

A Comparative Study of the Performance and Efficacy of Different Types of Hammer Beater Heads Used in a Newly Developed Palm Kernel Nut Cracking Machine

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Abstract:

A newly developed palm kernel nut cracking machine was developed at the department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, University of Uyo, the work was aimed at alleviating the difficulties faced by farmers in cracking their palm kernels manually. To further increase the efficiency and the capacity of the developed machine a study was carried out on the machine using 2-arm hammer beater, 3-arm hammer beater, and 4-arm hammer beater to establish the best beater that will result in high capacity and efficiency while using the palm kernel nut cracker. The research work which was titled "A comparative Study of the Performance and Efficiency of Different Types of Hammer Beater Heads Used in a Newly Developed Palm Kernel Nut Cracking Machine" was successfully completed. The

three different hammer beaters were tested on the newly developed palm kernel cracker and the result showed that in all the parameters tested none could emerge the overall best. However the work discovered that the best operating speed for all the three beaters was 1000rpm, for shorter cracking time the 4-arm hammer beater was the best, for least number of unbroken nuts 2-arm beater was the best, for highest number of cracked nuts 4-arm hammer beater was the best, for number of un-cracked nut, 4-arm beater had the least, and finally the result showed that 2-arm hammer beater had the highest overall efficiency of 88.37% , and 4-arm hammer beater had the best effective capacity. This variations notwithstanding the 2-arm hammer beater out-performed the others in many of the measured parameters and is recommended for the newly developed machine.

Keywords: comparative study, machine, palm kernel, cracker, effective capacity, performance, Efficiency, Types of hammer beaters.

Introduction

There are three common varieties of palm kernel nuts. Dura, Pisifera and Tenera. The Tenera is a hybrid of the Dura and the Pisifera. The Dura palm have kernels with a thick shell, the Pisifera palms have kernels with no shell, while the

Tenera palm have kernels with a thin shell (Anyane, 1966). In Nigeria it is the Tenera species that is commercially planted hence this research has designed and developed a cracker for the Tenera species, which is usually between 7-15 mm in length with shell thickness of 1.2mm. The palm tree is one of the greatest

economic assets a nation possess. The oils produce from oil palm namely palm oil and kernel oil are used for oil paints, margarine, candle, polish, soap making, glycerin and medical purposes. Oil palm are also used to produce biodiesel. The palm kernel shells are used as a source of energy by blacksmiths and other industries. They palm kernel shells are also used for making brake pads. Also the palm kernel cakes are used in making livestock feeds which are very rich in the essential nutrients required by livestock. For details on the uses of oil palm tree products see (FAO, 2002; FAO, 2004; Adebayo 2004; Emeka and Julius 2007; Asadullah *et al.*, 2014; Mba *et al.*, 2015; Mosarof *et al.*, 2015 and Norazura 2017). According to Badumus, (1991) Nigeria's oil palm exist in small oil palm plantation and wild groove, even though recently some large scale plantations have been developed. The need of oil palm processing machines suitable for small scale mills cannot be over emphasis. Machine involved in the palm oil mill process are: palm fruit sterilizer, palm fruit thresher, palm fruit digester, palm oil press machine, palm kernel cracker, palm kernel separator machine and palm kernel oil expeller machine. The design and development of these machines for large scale production has been the subject of many research work. These has resulted in the manufacture of sophisticated and complicated foreign made palm oil processing machines which are not suitable for our small scale production System (Akubuo and Eje, 2002; Antia *et al.*, 2014; Andoh, *et al.*, 2015).

Cracking palm nuts to release the kernel is an important issue within the palm kernel oil industry. There are basically two methods of this processing: the manual method and the mechanised method. The manual method of palm kernel nut cracking also known as the traditional method of palm kernel nut cracking makes use of stones to crack the nuts and kernels are separated by hand-picking from the shell simultaneously. This method is time – consuming and labour-intensive. The method cannot meet the demand of the growing international and domestic market. The method employs the principle of impact force to crack

the nuts so as to bring out kernel. This is usually done by placing about 4-6 nuts on a flat stone and using another stone as hammer to crack them (Babatunde *et al.*, 1988; Babatunde and Okoli 1988; Asoiro and Udo, 2013; Fashing *et al.*, 2017). The output sometime may be up to 50kg of kernel in a working day per worker, hence it is usually done by women and children. The mechanised palm kernel nut cracking also known as the modern method palm kernel nut cracking are often of centrifugal type. In this method nuts are fed into a cracking chamber where they are impacted upon by metal beaters turning at high speeds thereby throwing the nuts against a cracking ring (Cornish, 1991). The nuts impinge the wall at random orientation, but with repeated impact due to bouncing until they are discharged, cracked or uncracked albeit with much kernel breakage Ibiyeye *et al.*, (2022). Usually mechanised palm kernel nut crackers are designed with adjustment in speed for acceptable cracking efficiency. According to Ibiyeye *et al.*, (2022) knowledge of the force required for nut cracking to achieve minimum impact is important for improvement of the existing mechanised palm kernel nut crackers. They maintained that certain factors affect the cracking efficiency of the nut crackers. These factors are: (i) the size of nut (ii) the moisture content of nuts (iii) crackers rotor speed and (iv) fed rates. A number of researcher have work on the relationship of this factors to cracking efficiency (Antia *et al.*, 2014). Alade *et al.*, (2020) developed a modified palm kernel nut cracker from the conventional palm kernel nut cracker available in the Nigerian market. Performance analysis of the cracker using Minitab17 shows that efficiency of the machine was influenced by nut sizes and variation in the selected feed rates. The result indicated that the modified palm kernel nut cracker is suitable for processing palm nuts of all sizes when operated at moderate feed rates. It is important to note that the efficiency, capacity and output/hour of the palm kernel nut cracking machine depends on several factors, but in this work emphasis is on shaft speed and the type of cracker hammer/beater used. These two factors influence on the quality of cracked palm kernel nuts will be of great significance to palm kernel nut cracking machine producers,

since it will help them decide on the optimum number of arms a hammer cracker/ beater should have for quality cracking of palm kernel nuts (Offiong, 2024).

The objective of this project is to carry out a comparative study of the efficacy of different types of hammer beaters used in a newly developed palm kernel nut cracking machine. The effects of different types of arm hammer cracker/ beater in a palm kernel nut cracking machine on the quality of palm kernel nuts cracked and output when shaft speed is varied will be x-rayed in this study.

Materials and Method

Materials / Equipment

The materials and equipment used for this work include the newly designed and produced palm kernel cracking machine, different types of arm beater heads, timer, dried palm kernel nuts, collecting pans, sorters, tachometer for measurement of speed, and Microsoft Excel 2010 with Windows 7 software. The newly developed machine and 3 types of arm beater heads can be seen in Figures 2.1-2.3.

Description of the functional Components of the Newly Developed Cracker

The functional components of the newly developed cracker machine are: Hopper, Cracking Chamber, Power Transmission Shaft, bearing and bearing housing, pulley, and cracking mechanism.

A. **Hopper:** The hopper is connected to the conveying channel that leads to the cracking chamber. It is constructed as a truncated square base pyramid with mild steel sheet metal of 1.4mm gauge.

B. **Cracking Chamber:** The cracking chamber is cylindrical in shape with diameter 370 mm. It is made of a mild steel plate of 3mm thickness. The front and the rear ends of the chamber are covered with circular plates of the same material, thickness and diameter. The internal walls of the cylinder are lined with 12mm iron rods to form the cracking ring.

C. **Power Transmission Shaft:** The power transmission shaft is made of a 25mm diameter by 1200mm length rod of tool steel with two, three, or four-arm beaters welded to one end and a pulley pinned down the other end with a pillow bearing.

D. **Bearing and Bearing Housing:** Two UC 206, 30mm diameter pillow block bearing are used. The bearing housing is used to hold the bearing firmly to the frame, while the bearing itself holds the shaft in position to minimize friction during rotation.

E. **Pulley:** Two pulleys of different diameters are used in the design. The pulley is the device that transmit power from prime mover to the cracking mechanism shaft, via two v-belts. The smaller pulley connected to the prime mover is 50mm in diameter while the larger pulley connected to the shaft of the cracking machine is 80mm in diameter.

F. **Cracking Mechanism:** The 2, 3 or 4-arm hammer crack the kernel nut by beating it against the wall of the cracking chamber. The walls of the cracking chambers are lined with 12mm iron rods to form the cracking ring. The hammers are placed at the angle 180° , or 90° or 120° to each other around the shaft. The rotation of the shaft enable the hammers to hit the kernel laterally and let out the seed from the palm nut in a neat form (Offiong, 2024). See Figure 2.3 for the complete views of the two arm three arm, and four arm beater head/ shafts.

Operating Principles of the Newly Developed Palm Kernel Cracker

The Palm Kernel nuts are fed into the cracking chamber through the hopper, and the hoppers slanting nature facilitates the smooth movement of the kernels as feeding continues. Power is transmitted to the rotor from the prime mover through the v-belt. As the nut are fed from the hopper at moderate speed through the centralized hole in the flywheel, the centrifugal rotating arms- hammer beats the palm kernel against the cracking chamber giving rise to a very great impact force that eventually cracked the palm nuts. The cracked kernels and shells thereafter passed into the lower circumference

of the cracking chamber and are collected for separation. Figure 1 shows the newly produced palm kernel nut cracking machine and Figure 2

shows the exploded view of the newly developed machine.

Figure 1. Three Dimensional Model of the Developed Palm Kernel Nut Cracking Machine

Figure 2. Exploded View of Model Components of the Developed Palm Kernel Nut Cracking Machine

Figure 3. Types of Hammers Use in the Developed Palm Kernel Nut Cracking Machine

Method

Determination of evaluation parameters

Evaluation parameters for the developed crackers include Effective capacity (EC), cracking efficiency (CE), performance efficiency (PE), split-nut loss (%), (SL), (UL), un-cracked less (%); and overall efficiency (OE). These parameters can be calculated using equation (15-20) respectively.

$$EC=M/T \quad (15)$$

$$CE=[N_{cr}/N_{to}].100 \quad (16)$$

$$PE=[N_{wh}/N_{to}].100 \quad (17)$$

$$SL=[N_{br}/N_{to}].100 \quad (18)$$

$$UL=[N_{uc}/N_{to}].100 \quad (19)$$

$$OE=CE \times PE \quad (20)$$

$$N_{br}=N_{to} - (N_{wh} + N_{uc}) \quad (21)$$

$$N_{cr}=N_{wh} + N_{br} \quad (22)$$

Where M is total mass of palm nuts fed into the hopper (kg); T is total time taken by the cracked mixture to leave the chute (h) [Cornish, 1991]; N_{to} is the total number of kernel nuts fed into the hopper; N_{cr} is the total number of cracked kernel [damaged and undamaged] after cracking; N_{wh} is the number of whole [un-broken] kernel nut after cracking; N_{br} is the number of broken kernel nuts after cracking; and N_{uc} is the total number of un-cracked kernel nuts after cracking. In the experiment a constant volume of kernel to which N_{to} and M has been assigned will be employed and equation (21) and equation (22) will be used in the calculation of N_{br} and N_{cr} respectively. This means that for every cracking operation during the experiment only shaft speed, N_{wh} , N_{cu} , and the cracking time T will be recorded. N_{br} and N_{cr} will have to be calculated.

Experimental Procedure

A constant volume cylindrical container of diameter of 0.174m and height 0.180m is used in

measuring the palm kernel nut for the cracking experiment. The container was examined and found to contain an average of 640 palm kernel nuts weighing 3kg (3000grams) at full load. Using this container 640 palm kernel nuts were used to test the developed palm kernel cracking machine when assembled with four arm hammer beater. Speed was determined by the use of a tachometer. The procedure is that each set of the 640 palm kernel nuts was cracked at the shaft speed of 800, 1000, 1200, 1400 and 1600 rpm and the total number of whole kernel nuts and total number of un-cracked kernel nuts sorted. In each case the total mass of palm kernel nut fed into hopper together with the time taken by the cracked mixture to leave the chute was recorded. These data were then analyzed using Microsoft excel 2010 of window 7.

Results and Discussion

The result of the test using 3 types of arm hammer cracking shaft is shown below; Figure 3.0 is the sample of the palm kernel that was fed into the newly developed palm kernel cracking machine for cracking using 2-arm hammer, 3-arm hammer, and 4-arm hammer.

arm hammer and 4-arm hammer. Tables 3.1-3.4 show the result of the various parameters measured as it relates to quality of output, and Figures 3.1-3.7 show the performance efficiencies and effective capacity while using the 2-arm hammer, 3-arm hammer, and 4-arm hammer.

Figure 4. Sample of the Palm Kernel Nuts that were cracked in the Newly Developed Palm Kernel Nut Cracking Machine using 2-Arm Hammer, 3-Arm Hammer, and 4-Arm Hammer

Table 1. Number of Whole Nuts (Nwh) Processed Using 2-Arm Hammer Beater, 3-Arm Hammer Beater, and 4-Arm Hammer Beater

Speed of beater shaft	2-Arm Beater shaft	3-Arm Beater shaft	4-Arm Beater shaft
800	431	428	473
1000	581	541	529
1200	415	475	368
1400	296	305	267
1600	258	210	209

Table 2. Number of Un-Cracked Nuts (Nuc) Processed Using 2-Arm Hammer Beater, 3-Arm Hammer Beater, and 4-Arm Hammer Beater

Speed of beater shaft	2-Arm Beater shaft	3-Arm Beater shaft	4-Arm Beater shaft
800	71	33	21
1000	17	12	11
1200	6	6	8
1400	4	5	6
1600	3	2	1

Table 3. Number of Unbroken Nuts (Nbr) Processed Using 2-Arm Hammer Beater, 3-Arm Hammer Beater, and 4-Arm Hammer Beater

Speed of beater shaft	2-Arm Beater shaft	3-Arm Beater shaft	4-Arm Beater shaft
800	138	179	146
1000	42	87	100
1200	219	159	264
1400	340	330	367
1600	379	428	430

Table 4. Number of Cracked Nuts (Ncr) Processed Using 2-Arm Hammer Beater, 3-Arm Hammer Beater, and 4-Arm Hammer Beater

Speed of beater shaft	2-Arm Beater shaft	3-Arm Beater shaft	4-Arm Beater shaft
800	569	607	619
1000	623	628	629
1200	634	634	632
1400	636	635	634
1600	637	638	639

Figure 4 show the palm kernel nuts that were processed in the newly developed palm nut cracking machine palm kernel nuts with moisture content 10-12% were used for the experiment (Offiong, 2024).

Table 1 shows the number of whole nuts processed using 2-arm hammer beater, 3-arm hammer beater, and 4-arm hammer beater. The result shows that for the 3 different types of hammer beaters used; the shaft speed of 1000 rpm has the highest number of whole nuts cracked. 2-arm hammer beater has 581, 3-arm hammer beater has 541 and 4-arm hammer beater has 529. The highest number of whole nuts occurred at 2-arm hammer beater. The best performing arm hammer beater with variation in shaft speed is however, the 2-arm hammer beater, which is closely followed by the 3-arm hammer beater, and the 4-arm hammer beater, which is the last. This same trend was observed by Offiong (2024)

Table 2 shows the number of Un-cracked nuts processed using 2-arm hammer beater, 3-arm hammer beater and 4-arm hammer beater. The result shows that at the shaft speed of 1600 rpm the number of un-cracked nuts were least. 3 for 2-arm hammer beater, 2 for 3-arm hammer beater and 1 for 4-arm hammer beater. The shaft speed of 1400 rpm followed with 4 for 2-arm hammer beater, 5 for 3-arm hammer beater and

6 for 4-arm hammer beater. At shaft speed of 800-1000rpm; 4-arm hammer beater had the least number of un-cracked nuts, however, at the shaft speed of 1200-1600, 2-arm hammer beater and 3-arm hammer beater performed at the same level, having lesser quantities of un-cracked nuts than the 4-arm hammer beater (Ndegwe, 1987; Ibrahim, *et al.*, 2016; Okoli, 2022).

Table 3 shows the number of unbroken nuts processed using 2-arm hammer beater, 3-arm hammer beater, and 4-arm hammer beater. The shaft speed of 1000 rpm has the least number of unbroken nuts; 2-arm hammer beater has 42, 3-arm hammer beater has 87, and 4-arm hammer has 100. As the shaft speed increases the result shows that 2-arm hammer beater has the least number of unbroken nuts followed by 3-arm hammer beater. For less unbroken nuts 2-arm beater is recommended for use on the newly developed palm kernel cracking machine. Offiong (2024) and several authors have made similar observations (Olugunagba, 2012; Udo *et al.*, 2015; Taofik *et al.*, 2019)

Table 4 shows number of cracked nuts processed using 2-arm hammer beater, 3-arm hammer beater, and 4-arm hammer beater. The result shows that the highest number of cracked nuts occurred at the shaft speed of 1600 rpm, which is 637 at 2-arm hammer beater, 638 at 3-arm hammer beater, and 639 at 4-arm hammer

beater. This is closely followed by 1400 rpm shaft speed. As the shaft speed is increased with the number of arm hammer beaters the result showed that 4-arm hammer beater had the highest number of cracked nuts followed by 3-arm hammer beater and 2-arm hammer beater. For increased number of cracked nuts, using 4-arm hammer beater is recommended. There is

however, a repercussion because for increased cracking at high speed using the 4-arm hammer beater also comes with increase in number of broken nuts. The work of Offiong (2024) observed this and many other authors (Olugunagba, 2012; Udo *et al.*, 2015; Taofik *et al.*, 2019).

Figure 5. Cracking Time of the Palm Kernel Nuts with Variation in Shaft Speed Using 2-Arm Hammer Beater, 3-Arm Hammer Beater, and 4-Arm Hammer Beater

Figure 5 shows Cracking Time of the Palm Kernel Nuts with Variation in Shaft Speed Using 2-Arm Hammer Beater, 3-Arm Hammer Beater, and 4-Arm Hammer Beater. Two-arm hammer beater has the highest cracking time among the 3 hammer beaters the curve is above all the three and gradually slopes down indicating that as the shaft speed increases the cracking time decreases. 3-arm hammer beater curve is next to that of 2-arm hammer beater it requires lesser cracking time than the 2-arm hammer beater. The curve drops gradually as the shaft speed increases indicating that as the speed increases the cracking time decreases, although there was an increase at 1400 rpm but after that the cracking time continued to decrease with increasing speed. The lower curve is the curve of the 4-arm hammer beater showing that it has the lowest cracking time. The downward sloping of the curve from left to right means that as the

shaft speed is increasing the cracking time is decreasing. Comparing the three types of arm hammer beaters, if shorter cracking time is required then the 4-arm hammer beater is recommended. Previous works have made similar observations regarding cracking time that it increases with increase in shaft speed this probably because it increases impact and attrition between the surface of the cracking chamber and the kernel nuts (Ndegwe, 1987; Ibrahim, *et al.*, 2016; Okoli, 2022; Offiong, 2024).

Figure 6 shows the graph of Effective Capacity of the Palm Kernel Nut Cracking Machine with Variation in Shaft Speed Using 2-Arm Hammer Beater, 3-Arm Hammer Beater, and 4-Arm Hammer Beater. The three curves slope from right to left indicating that as the shaft speed increases the effective capacity of the three beaters also increases with the 4-arm hammer beater having the highest effective capacity,

followed by the 3-arm hammer beater and then the 2-arm hammer beater. The effective capacity of the 3-arm hammer beater dropped at the speed of 1400rpm, but thereafter picked up again. Comparing the 2, 3, 4-arm hammer

beaters it is recommended that for effective capacity the 4-arm hammer beater be used. Offiong (2024) has equally made this observation.

Figure 6. Effective Capacity of the Palm Kernel Nut Cracking Machine with Variation in Shaft Speed Using 2-Arm Hammer Beater, 3-Arm Hammer Beater, and 4-Arm Hammer Beater

Figure 7. Cracking Efficiency of the Palm Kernel Cracking Machine with Variation in Shaft Speed Using 2-Arm Hammer Beater, 3-Arm Hammer Beater, and 4-Arm Hammer Beater

Figure 7 shows the Cracking Efficiency of the Palm Kernel Cracking Machine with Variation in

Shaft Speed Using 2-Arm Hammer Beater, 3-Arm Hammer Beater, and 4-Arm Hammer

Beater. The three curves in the graph show that as the shaft speed was increased at lower speeds the curve of the 4-arm hammer was above, followed by the curve of the 3-arm hammer beater and then that of the 2-arm hammer beater, which means at lower speeds the cracking efficiency of the 4-arm hammer was higher than the 3-arm hammer beater and the 2-arm hammer beater. As the speed continue to increase the curves also continue to rise towards the right, and at 1200 -1600rpm the three curves become very close to one another. As the shaft speed increases the cracking efficiency of the 2, 3, 4-

arm hammer beaters also increases, until 1200-1600 rpm where the cracking efficiency becomes almost aligned for all of them. To recommend the best arm beater to use for high cracking efficiency, at lower shaft speed the 4-arm hammer beater is recommended, but for shaft speeds above 1200 rpm the graph shows that all the three have high cracking efficiencies therefore any selection will be appropriate. Offiong, (2024) and multiple authors in their respective works have made the same observations (Ndegwe, 1987; Ibrahim, *et al.*, 2016; Okoli, 2022)

Figure 8. Performance Efficiency of the Palm Kernel Cracking Machine with Variation of Shaft Speed Using 2-Arm Hammer Beater, 3-Arm Hammer Beater, and 4-Arm Hammer Beater

Figure 8 is the graph of Performance Efficiency of the Palm Kernel Cracking Machine with Variation of Shaft Speed Using 2-Arm Hammer Beater, 3-Arm Hammer Beater, and 4-Arm Hammer Beater. The three curves representing, 2-arm hammer, 3-arm hammer and 4-arm hammer beaters all have the same shape. They all rise and peak at the shaft speed of 1000rpm as the speed is increasing with the performance efficiency, indicating that the shaft speed of 1000rpm presented the best performance efficiency for all the three arm beaters. The peak of the 2-arm hammer beater is however, higher than the peak of the other two. The 2-arm beater has performance efficiency of 90.78%. after the peak all the three curves gradually sloped to the right indicating that all the beaters attained optimum performance efficiency at the speed of 1000rpm and further shaft speed increase only

resulted in decrease of performance efficiencies of the 2,3, 4-arm hammer beaters. The 2-arm hammer beater has the highest performance efficiency and is recommended, followed by the 3-arm hammer beater. This work agrees with previous authors who have worked in this area (Ndegwe, 1987; Ibrahim, *et al.*, 2016; Okoli, 2022, Offiong, 2024).

Figure 9 shows the graph of Split-Nut Loss % of Palm Kernel Nuts Processed with Variation of Shaft Speed Using 2-Arm Hammer Beater, 3-Arm Hammer Beater, and 4-Arm Hammer Beater. The three curves exhibited the same trend, the three curves all show a depression at the speed of 1000 rpm as the speed continue to increase the curves started rising up, the curve of the 2-arm hammer beater which was down above the speed of 1000rpm came in between the two other curves, but above 1400 rpm the

curve of the 3-arm hammer beater rose to meet with that of 4-arm hammer beater at 1600rpm. At 1000 rpm the 2-arm hammer beater has the lowest split-nut loss% which was followed by the 3-arm hammer beater. It is interesting to

note that to obtain minimum split nut losses it is most appropriate to use the 2-arm hammer beater. This has been confirmed by Offiong, (2024).

Figure 9. Split-Nut Loss % of Palm Kernel Nuts Processed with Variation of Shaft Speed Using 2-Arm Hammer Beater, 3-Arm Hammer Beater, and 4-Arm Hammer Beater

Figure 10. Un-Cracked Nut Loss % of Processed Palm Kernel Nuts with Variation of Shaft Speed Using 2-Arm Hammer Beater, 3-Arm Hammer Beater, and 4-Arm Hammer Beater

Figure 10 shows the graph of Un-Cracked Nut Loss % of Processed Palm Kernel Nuts with Variation of Shaft Speed Using 2-Arm Hammer Beater, 3-Arm Hammer Beater, and 4-Arm Hammer Beater. The curve of the 2-arm hammer beater, the 3-arm hammer beater, and the 4-arm hammer beater all have nearly the same shape, dropping drastically from 800-

1000rpm and then dropping gradually to 1600rpm. This indicate that as the shaft speed was increasing the number of un-cracked nut was decreasing and the reduction was more drastic at the speed of 1000 rpm. Further increase in speed saw more drastic decrease with the 2-arm hammer beater and towards the end of the speed increase all the three arm beaters

almost aligned. From the graph the 2-arm hammer beater is the best to use for un-cracked nut loss% reduction. This observation is in harmony with previous works reviewed (Ndegwe, 1987; Antia *et al.*, 2014; Ibrahim, *et al.*,

2016; Okoli, 2022; Offiong, 2024). The graph also clearly shows that as the shaft speed is increased irrespective of the arm hammer beater that is used the number of un-cracked nut loss % reduces.

Figure 11. Overall Efficiency (OE) of the Palm Kernel Nut Cracking Machine with Variation of Shaft Speed Using 2-Arm Hammer Beater, 3-Arm Hammer Beater, and 4-Arm Hammer Beater

Figure 11 is the graph of Overall Efficiency (OE) of the Palm Kernel Nut Cracking Machine with Variation of Shaft Speed Using 2-Arm Hammer Beater, 3-Arm Hammer Beater, and 4-Arm Hammer Beater. The three curves representing 2-arm beater, 3-arm hammer beater and 4-arm hammer beater exhibit the same trend, although the rate of increase and decrease may be different. The three curves all rose and peaked at 1000 rpm where after they decreased at various rate as the shaft speed continued to increased up to 1600 rpm, at 1400 rpm and beyond the curve of the 4-arm beater again rose as the speed reached 1600rpm. The implication is that all the three arm beaters have optimum overall efficiency at the speed of 1000 rpm, with the 2-arm beater having the highest overall efficiency of 88.37%. The result indicate that the best speed for operating the three arm beaters is 1000rpm and the best arm hammer beater for best overall efficiency is the 2-arm hammer beater. The three curves all show that as the speed increases the overall efficiencies of the

three arm beaters used on the newly developed palm kernel cracking machine also increases, but as it reaches an optimum value it starts decreasing except for the 4-arm beater that rose again between 1400 rpm to 1600rpm. Closely related observation has earlier on been mentioned by those who conducted similar experiments (Olugunagba, 2012; Udo *et al.*, 2015; Fashing *et al.*, 2017; Taofik *et al.*, 2019; Offiong 2024).

Conclusions

A comparative study of the performance and efficacy of different types of hammer beater heads used in a newly developed palm kernel nut cracking machine has been carried out. From the findings of the work the following conclusions have been drawn:

1. The work has shown that for shorter cracking time the best arm beater to use is the 4-arm hammer beater

2. The work has shown that for high overall efficiency the best arm beater to use is the 2-arm hammer beater which has the highest overall efficiency of 88.47%.
3. The work has equally shown that the best shaft speed to operate the three arm hammer beaters is 1000 rpm
4. It has also been observed that the 2-arm hammer beater is the best to use for un-cracked nut loss% reduction
5. The 2-arm hammer beater has the lowest split-nut loss% which was followed by the 3-arm hammer beater
6. The 2-arm hammer beater has the highest performance efficiency of 90.78% and is recommended, followed by the 3-arm hammer beater.
7. To recommend the best arm beater to use for high cracking efficiency, at lower shaft speed the 4-arm hammer beater is recommended, but for shaft speeds above 1200 rpm the graph shows that all the three have high cracking efficiencies therefore any selection will be appropriate.

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